

**JIZZAKH TRAINING CENTER FOR OLYMPIC AND PARALYMPIC SPORTS -
GENERAL PHYSICAL FITNESS INDICATORS ANALYSIS OF ATHLETES**

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Abstract: this article was prepared in the framework of an innovative project on the topic “selection, selection, selection, prediction and creation of digital technologies for the implementation of higher sports achievement development moni - Toring in sports educational institutions”, registered with the state registration number ALM-202306161313, which is carried out at the Institute of physical education and sports scientific research.

Keywords: Olympic, Paralympic, physical fitness, adjectives, agility, endurance, flexibility, strength, endurance, readiness indicators.

**АНАЛИЗ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ОБЩЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ
УЧАЩИХСЯ-СПОРТСМЕНОВ ЦЕНТРА ПОДГОТОВКИ К ОЛИМПИЙСКИМ И
ПАРАЛИМПИЙСКИМ ВИДАМ СПОРТА Г. ДЖИЗАК**

Аннотация: данная статья подготовлена в рамках инновационного проекта по теме “Создание цифровых технологий для внедрения мониторинга отбора, отбора, прогнозирования и развития высших спортивных достижений в спортивных образовательных учреждениях”, реализуемого в научно - исследовательском институте физической культуры и спорта, зарегистрированном под государственным регистрационным номером ALM-202306161313 в том числе вопросы эффективности внедрения мониторинга развития видов.

Ключевые слова: олимпийский, Паралимпийский, физическая подготовка, качества, скорость, выносливость, гибкость, сила, выносливость, подготовительные показатели.

INTRODUCTION

The Institute of physical education and Sports Scientific Research compared the general physical fitness of student-athletes studying at Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers in khududud, the highest level of physical fitness indicators of the population established in the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 16, 2021 PQ-5248 on “measures for the organization of

MAIN PART

The purpose of the study: consists in determining the physical fitness indicators of student-athletes who are preparing for Olympic and Paralympic sports in training centers.

Research tasks: determination of physical fitness indicators of student-athletes;

Analysis of the results: the Institute of Physical Education and Sports Scientific Research compared the general physical fitness of student-athletes studying at Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers in the territories, the highest level of physical fitness indicators of the population, established in the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 16, 2021 PQ-5248 on “measures to

The “speed” quality of the student-athletes of the 5th grade (boys) of this center (60 m.ga running) test scores averaged 10.49 s. it was found to be equal to, with a high overall set regulatory requirement of 10.0 s for this type of test. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.49 s. showed that ga is low. The quality of “speed ” of this class (girls) student-athletes (60 m.ga running) test scores averaged 10.72 s. it was found to be equal to, with a high normative requirement of 11.5 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.78 s. indicates that ga is high.

Grade 5 (boys) was conducted to determine the “endurance” quality of student-athletes (1,000 m.ga running) test performance averages 3 min, 74 s. was, the overall set demand high was 3 min, 54 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.2 s. showing that ga is low. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (1000 m.ga running) test performance averages 4 min, 21 s. was, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 4.45 min, equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.24 s. indicates that ga is good.

The test scores for Grade 5 (boys) student-athletes to determine the quality of “strength” were averaged 8.69 times, with a high normative requirement of 9 times, as evidenced by the difference in performance being lower by 0.31 times. The test scores average for this class (girls) student-athletes to determine the quality of their “strength” (bending hands while leaning on the ground) was 18 times, the normative requirement high was 14 times, the difference between indicators was 4 times higher.

Grade 5 (boys) was conducted to determine the “agility” quality of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.74 s. established, the normative demand high is 7.9 s. is equal to, 0.16 s. ga indicates that it is good. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” from student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 8.14 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8.2 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.06 s. ga showed that it was good.

The average student-athlete performance of this class (boys) in the long jump test from where they stand is 174.23 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand 180 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 5.77 sm.ga it was found to be low. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes by this type of test is 169 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 165 sm.ga equal, difference between indicators 4 sm.ga indicates that it is high.

Grade 5 (boys) student-athletes ' test scores of +9.77, which were conducted to determine the quality of “Flexion” (forward flexion without bending the leg knees in the sitting position). sm.ni organized, high normative demand index +10 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 0.23 sm.ga indicates low size. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes on the quality of “flexibility” is 16.50 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand 14 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators 2.50 sm.ga showed high.

The quality of “speed” of the student-athletes of the 6th grade (boys) of the Jizzakh Olympic and Paralympic Sports Training Center (60 m.ga run) by test scores, with an average of 9.97 s. it was found to be equal to, with a high normative requirement of 10.0 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.03 s. ga was found to be high. The quality of “speed ” of this class (girls) student-athletes (60 m.ga running) test scores averaged 10.57 s. it was found to be equal to, with a high normative requirement of 11.5 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.93 s. indicates that ga is high.

Grade 6 (boys) was held to determine the “endurance” quality of student-athletes (1,000 m.ga running) test performance averages 3 min, 78 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 3 min, 54 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.24 s. it was found to be low to. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (1000 m.ga running) test performance averages 4 min, 30 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 4 min, 45 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.15 s. it's high equal to.

The test scores for Grade 6 (boys) student-athletes to determine the quality of “strength” were averaged 8.27 times, with a high normative requirement of 9 times, as evidenced by the difference in performance being lower by 0.73 times. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes in tests performed to determine the quality of “strength” (bending hands with a base on the ground) was 20 times, the high rate of normative demand is 14 times, the difference between indicators is 6 times more.

Grade 6 (boys) was conducted to determine the “agility” quality of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.48 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory

demand is 7 min, 9 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.42 s. ga was determined to be good. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” from student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 8.23 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8 min, 2 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.03 s. Ga showed that it was a pass.

The average student-athlete performance of this class (boys) in the long jump test from where they stand is 182.40 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand 180 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 2.40 sm.ga it was found to be low. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes by this type of test is 159.33 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 165 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 5.67 sm.ga indicates that it is low.

Grade 6 (boys) student-athletes' test scores for “Flexion” quality (forward flexion without bending the leg knees in the sitting position) were averaged +10.27 sm.ni organized, high normative demand index +10 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 0.27 sm.ga shows the high end. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes on the quality of “flexibility” is +13.0 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand +14 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators 1 sm.ga indicates that it is low.

Grade 7 (boys) was conducted to determine the “endurance” quality of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test performance averages 5 min, 97 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8 min, 10 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 2.13 s. ga showed that it was high. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test scores averaged 6 min, 17 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 10 min, equal to, the difference between indicators is 3 min, 83 s. indicates that ga is good.

The average of 7th grade (boys) student-athletes in test scores performed to determine the quality of “strength” was 11.67 times, with a high normative requirement of 12 times, as evidenced by the difference in performance being 0.33 times lower. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes in hand bending (marta) test scores performed to determine the quality of “strength” was 15.63 times, the high normative requirement is 15 times, the difference between indicators is a sign that it is good for 0.63 times.

Grade 7 (boys) was conducted to determine the “agility” quality of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.38 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 7.0 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.38 s. it was found to be low to. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” from student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.42 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8.0 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.58 s. ga showed that it was high.

The average performance of this 7th grade (boys) student-athlete in the long jump test from where they stand is 202.24 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 215 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 12.76 sm.ga it was found to be low. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes by this type of test is 188 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand 180 sm.ga equal, difference between indicators 8 sm.ga indicates that it is high.

Grade 7 (boys) student-athletes' test scores of +12.35, which were conducted to determine the quality of “Flexion” (forward flexion without bending the leg knees in the sitting position). sm.ni organized, high normative demand index +10 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 2.35 sm.ga shows the high end. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes on the quality of “flexibility” is +14.25 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand +14 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 0.25 sm.ga indicates that it is high.

Jizzakh was held to determine the quality of “endurance” of the 8th grade (boys) student-athletes of the Olympic and Paraolympic Sports Training Center (2000 m.ga running) test scores averaged 6 min, 08 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8 min, 10 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 2 min, 02 s. ga was determined to be good. This class (girls)

was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test scores averaged 6 min, 39 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 10 min, equal to, the difference between indicators is 3.61 s. indicates that ga is high.

The average of 8th grade (boys) student-athletes in test scores performed to determine the quality of “strength” was 8.11 times, with a high normative requirement of 12 times, as evidenced by the difference in performance being a pass of 3.89 times. The test scores average for this class (girls) student-athletes to determine the quality of their “strength” (bending hands while leaning on the ground) was 32 times, the high normative requirement is 15 times, the difference between indicators is 17 times more.

This class (boys) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.33 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 7 min, equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.33 s. it was found to be low to. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” from student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.64 s. formed, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8 min, equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.36 s. ga showed that it was good.

In the long jump from the standing position, the student-athlete average for this class (boys) is 205.56 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 215 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 9.44 sm.ga it was found to be low. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes by this type of test is 186.86 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand 180 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 6.86 sm.ga indicates that it is high.

Grade 9 (boys) was conducted to determine the “endurance” quality of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test performance averages 8 min, 22 s. established, the normative demand high is 7 min, 50 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.72 s. it was found to be low to. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test scores averaged 9 min, 48 s. established, the normative demand high is 9 min, 50 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.02 s. indicates that ga is good.

The average for the results of the test conducted to determine the quality of “strength” of the student-athletes of the 9th grade (boys) was 14.40 times, the high rate of normative demand is 14 times, as evidenced by the fact that the difference between indicators is 0.40 times higher. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes in hand bending (marta) test scores, conducted to determine the quality of “strength”, was 16.44 times, the high rate of normative demand is 16 times, the difference between indicators indicates that it is good for 0.44 times.

Grade 9 (boys) was conducted to determine the “agility” quality of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.27 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 7.0 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.27 s. it was found to be low to. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” from student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.58 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 8.0 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.42 s. ga showed that it was low.

Student-athlete Grade 9 (boys) in long jump from standing position average of 227.40 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 230 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 2.60 sm.ga it was found to be low. The average performance of this class (girls) student-athletes by this type of test is 183.56 sm.ni established, high rate of regulatory demand 185 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 1.44 sm.ga indicates that it is low.

Forward flexion from the gymnastics seat without bending the knees of the feet test results in Grade 9 (boys) student-athlete averages +14.80 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand +13 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 1.80 sm.ga indicates low. The “flexibility” quality of this class (girls) student-athletes (bending forward without bending the knees of the feet from the gymnastic seat) has a test score average of +16.78 CM. it turned out to be equal to, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 16 cm. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.78 CM. indicates that ga is low.

Grade 10 (boys) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test scores averaged 7 mins, 00 s. established, the normative demand high is 7 min, 50 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.50 s. it was found to be low to.

The average for the results of the test conducted to determine the quality of “strength” of student-athletes in Grade 10 (boys) was 12.65 times, the high rate of normative demand is 14 times, as evidenced by the fact that the difference between indicators is lower by 1.35 times.

This 10th grade (boys) was conducted to determine the quality of “agility” of student-athletes (3x10 m.ga mokisimon run) test scores averaged 7.21 s. established, the high indicator of regulatory demand is 7.0 s. equal to, the difference between the indicators is 0.21 s. ga showed that it was low.

The Standing place long jump student-athlete 10th grade (boys) average is 224.88 sm.ni organized, high normative Demand Index 230 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 5.12 sm.ga showed low.

10th grade (boys) student-athletes (bending forward from the gymnastics seat without bending the knees of the feet) test scores average +11.65 sm.ni organized, high index of regulatory demand +13 sm.ga equal, the difference between indicators is 1.35 sm.ga indicates low.

Grade 11 (boys) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” for student-athletes (2000 m.ga running) test performance averages 7 min, 32 s. established, the normative demand high is 7 min, 50 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.28 s. ga has been found to be high. This class (girls) was conducted to determine the quality of “endurance” of student-athletes (200 m.ga running) test scores averaged 9 min, 27 s. established, the normative demand high is 9 min, 50 s. equal to, the difference between indicators is 0.23 s. indicates that ga is high.

CONCLUSION

The average for the test results of this class (boys) to determine the quality of “strength” of student-athletes was 13.75 times, the high rate of normative demand is 14 times, as evidenced by the fact that the difference between indicators is lower by 0.25 times. The test scores average for this class (girls) student-athletes to determine the quality of their “strength” (bending hands while leaning on the ground) was 22 times, the high normative requirement is 16 times, the difference between indicators is 6 times more.

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